

THERMOMECHANICAL EVALUATION OF SISAL-PLA COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Sisal fibre-PLA composites were compression moulded with V_f up to 0.6 with mean flexural strengths up to 279 MPa. DMTA revealed the glass transition temperature (T_g) to fall as V_f increased. Hot stage microscopy was used to follow spherulitic growth of PLA on sisal fibre bundles. Fibre to matrix adhesion was measured by microbond shear.

Keywords: sisal fibre composites, polylactic acid (PLA), flexural strength, DMTA, hot stage digital microscopy, spherulitic crystal growth, microbond shear strength.

INTRODUCTION

Polylactic acid polymer (PLA) is a commercially available bio-polymer of considerable interest for structural composites [1]. PLA is a semicrystalline thermoplastic polyester formulated from renewable resources with a glass transition temperature (T_g) of between 50 and 60°C and a melting temperature (T_m) of 168 to 172°C. [2].

This paper focuses on structure-property relationships for bio-composites where both the matrix and the reinforcement are bio-sourced and biodegradable [3, 4]. Mechanical and dynamic mechanical behaviour of polylactic acid reinforced with unidirectional sisal fibre bundles are examined for composites with different fibre volume fractions, V_f . Composites were manufactured by compression moulding of unidirectionally aligned fibres and polymer sheets [5, 6]. Fibre volume fraction was determined by precision weighing of the components and density measurements. The influence of fibre volume fraction on dynamic mechanical properties was evaluated using dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA).

Understanding the interface characteristics is crucial for manufacture of good quality composites. The surfaces of natural fibre bundles embedded in a thermoplastic matrix act as a nucleating site for the spherulitic growth of thermoplastic crystals. Numerous nucleating sites on the surface of the fibre can result in the growth of laterally restricted spherulites forming a compact transcrystalline layer. Hot stage digital microscopy is used in this paper to follow spherulitic crystal growth of PLA on sisal fibre bundles. Strong interfacial adhesion between the fibre and the matrix is crucial for effective stress transfer in the composite. An improvement in interfacial shear strength has been reported for single fibre thermoplastic composites because of the presence of transcrystallinity [7].

The effect of fibre surface treatment with caustic soda on transcrystallinity and fibre to matrix adhesion is also examined in this paper with reference to previously published research [8, 9]. Thermal history, fibre surface modification and their influence on the adhesion of PLA to sisal fibres is investigated using the microbond shear test.

MATERIALS

PLA (Biomer 9000, $M_w = 180,000$ g/mol, melt flow index of 5g/10 min. at 2.16 kg/190°C, density of 1.27 g/cm³) used in this study was purchased from Biomer GmbH, Krailing, Germany. Sisal fibre bundles (*Agave sisalana*) were sourced in Tanzania. The density of sisal fibre bundles was 1.24 g/cm³ (Archimedes principle). Caustic soda was obtained from Sigma Aldrich, UK. Mould release agent used in composites manufacture was PAT-607/PCM and was purchased from E. P. Wurtz GmbH, Germany.

MANUFACTURE OF COMPOSITES

PLA foils: Polylactic acid granules were used as purchased, oven dried overnight at 50°C and compression moulded in foils of 0.3 – 0.4 mm thickness placing 5g of PLA between two steel plates (200 x 200 mm). Compression moulding was carried out in two stages. Firstly the PLA was consolidated at 190°C and low pressure for 10min. Secondly the PLA was compressed at 190°C and 0.1 MPa for 10 min. Foils were cooled down at room temperature for 24 h. Moulded foils were stored in polyethylene sealed bags at room temperature and 50% relative humidity. PLA foils were oven dried at 50°C overnight. The shape of the sheets was adjusted to fit in the compression mould for manufacture of composites.

Sisal fibre bundles: prior to processing, the fibres were washed for 2 hours at 90°C in water to remove all the dust particles and impurities. Fibres were dried using paper tissues at room temperature for 12 hours and then placed in a circulating air oven at 80°C overnight. Dried fibres were stored in sealed PE bags at room temperature with a calcium chloride dehumidifier.

Fibre treatment: some sisal fibres were treated with caustic soda. Fibres were immersed in 0.06 M NaOH solution for 48 hours, then rinsed with excess of distilled water and neutralised with dilute acetic acid (1 wt% solution). Fibres were dried as before.

Figure 1: PLA/sisal fibre composite (80 x 17 x 1 mm).

Composites processing: An aluminium compression mould was designed for composite manufacture. Aligned sisal fibres were combined with polymer sheets and compression moulded at 200°C at 0.1MPa for 3-5 min. After compression the composites were cooled down to 22°C with an applied pressure of 4MPa over a period of about 30

minutes. Composites were released from the mould and stored in PE sealed bags at 22°C and 50 % relative humidity. Samples (Figure 1) for three point bending flexural test and dynamic mechanical test were cut from the composites sheets using a jig saw. The fibre weight fraction was determined by precision weighting and converted into the volume fraction.

MICROSCOPY

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Compression moulded composites were embedded in an epoxy resin (Struers Specifix 40) and polished. A series of wet abrasive SiC papers was used (600-, 1200-, 2400- and 4000) for the polishing operation. Final polishing was done with 0.04 µm silica suspension on Struers MD Chem cloth. Samples were gold coated (Edwards Sputter coater model S 150 B) and inspected under the SEM microscope (JEOL 6310) at accelerating voltage of 10 kV. Microphotographs were used for qualitative analysis of interfacial bonding between sisal fibres and the polymer matrix (Figure 2 and 3). SEM imaged cross sections of composites revealed good fibre to matrix adhesion.

Figure 2: SEM photomicrographs of the polished cross-section of PLA/sisal composite ($V_f = 60$ vol. %).

Figure 3: Sisal fibre embedded in PLA matrix

Hot stage microscopy

Leica DME transmitted light optical microscope equipped with a Metler Toledo FP 82 hot stage and a FP 90 control unit was used to observe the spherulitic growth at the fibre to matrix interface. Photographs of the interface morphology were taken using a Lumenera Infinity 1 digital camera and Metler Toledo Studio Capture software.

Specimen preparation: a piece of sisal fibre (10 mm) was placed onto a glass slide and covered with a square of PLA foil. The set up was placed on an electrically heated hot plate heated up to 190°C and melted. The cover slip was slightly pressed onto the melted polymer sheet. The single fibre composite was transferred into the hot stage and heated up to 180°C for 10 min. to relax the previous thermal history. After this samples

were cooled down at cooling rate of 2, 5 and 10°C/min to a crystallization temperature of 140, 130 and 120°C. Once the temperature was reached samples were held at this temperature for up to 60 minutes to promote the growth of a transcrystalline layer (TCL) at the fibre to matrix interface.

Figure 4: Transcrystalline layer on sisal fibre treated with 6 wt% NaOH solution (cooling rate 5°C/min; isothermal crystallization at 130°C for 15 min.

Transcrystallinity

Figure 4 images a transcrystalline layer on sisal fibre treated with 6 wt% NaOH solution. The single fibre composite was heated up to 180°C, cooled down at the rate of 5°C/min and isothermally crystallized at 130°C for 15 minutes. It was found that annealing is necessary to create the TCL around the fibres. Untreated fibres at 130 and 140°C did not exhibit transcrystalline growth but individual spherulitic growth occurred. Caustic soda treated fibres promoted the creation of a TCL at the fibre to matrix interface possibly due to the formation of cellulose II at the fibre bundle surface and the removal of pectins. Caustic soda treatment is advantageous in forming well-defined TCLs at the fibre to thermoplastic matrix interface which is likely to improve stress transfer.

MICROBOND SHEAR TESTS

Sample preparation: A square of PLA (10 x 10 mm) was cut from the compression moulded sheet and stored in a dehumidified environment. A glass slide (76 x 26 x 1 mm) was wrapped in aluminium foil (thickness = 0.04 mm). Mould release agent (Wurth PAT-607/PCM) was applied on the top surface of the foil. A PLA square was placed on

top of the glass slide. The glass slide was placed on a hot plate ($T = 190\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and a sisal fibre bundle was dipped (using tweezers) in the edge of the molten PLA square. The melted polymer was covered with a glass cover slip ($22 \times 22 \times 0.15\text{ mm}$) and gently pressed with tweezers. After this, the sample was removed from the hot plate and air quenched. After 20 minutes the foil was peeled off. The fibre embedded in the plastic adhered to the cover slip was glued to a paper mount card ($65 \times 24 \times 0.22\text{ mm}$; gauge length of 10 mm). The embedded fibre length and fibre diameter were measured with an optical microscope (Leica DME, magnification $100\times$, transmitted light) equipped with a digital camera (Lumenera Infinity 1) and Studio Measure software (Metler Toledo). The microscope lens (scale bar) was calibrated using calibrated stage micrometer.

Test procedure: partially embedded fibres were pulled out from the matrix using an Instron 3369 tensile test machine with 10 kg (100 N) load cell at extension rate of 1 mm/min . Specimens were mounted on paper cards (gauge length 10 mm). The edges of the card were cut with a pair of scissors before the test. Failed samples were checked under the optical microscope to decide whether the fibre was pulled out from the matrix or not (fibre failure in tension) after the test. Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) was calculated using the following expression, where F_{max} is the maximum pull out strength, d is the fibre diameter and l_m is the length of the fibre embedded in the polymer matrix.

$$\tau = \frac{F_{\text{max}}}{\pi d l_m}$$

Statistical analysis

The failure at the interface was described with a two parameter Weibull distribution [8]. Weibull cumulative distribution function is given by the following equation:

$$P_f(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right]$$

Where P_f is the probability of failure, σ is the failure stress, σ_0 is the normalizing stress and m is a constant (Weibull modulus). Taking natural logarithms of both sides of the equation, the equation was converted into the form of straight line equation. The Weibull modulus and normalizing stress were calculated from the slope and y-intercept of the line equation.

$$\ln\left[-\ln(1 - P_f)\right] = m \ln x - m \ln \sigma_0$$

Figures 5 and 6 show typical microbond pull-out curves for untreated and caustic soda treated sisal fibres embedded in polylactic acid. The maximum debonding forces are not directly comparable because of the different embedded lengths of the fibres in the matrix. The shape of the curves is similar to those reported by Bannister [12]. At least 30 specimens were tested and 85 % of pull out test were successful. Due to the anisotropy, non-uniform cross section and surface roughness of the fibres the Weibull distribution of interfacial shear strength was expected (Figure 9 and 10). The interfacial shear strength for untreated and treated sisal fibres partially embedded in PLA matrix was $10.5 \pm 3.72\text{ MPa}$ and $15.3 \pm 5.96\text{ MPa}$, respectively. Thus caustic soda treatment improved the fibre to matrix adhesion but the Weibull parameters m were similar.

Figure 5: Typical load - displacement curves obtained from successful single fibre pull out tests of untreated sisal fibres.

Figure 6: Typical load - displacement curves obtained from successful single fibre pull out tests of caustic soda treated sisal fibres.

Figure 7: Sisal fibres without surface treatment. IFSS plotted as a Weibull distribution.

Figure 8: Caustic soda treated sisal fibres. IFSS plotted as a Weibull distribution.

FLEXURAL TEST

Manufactured composites were tested in three point bending on an Instron 3369 testing machine equipped with the load cell of 4.25 kg. The sample dimensions were adjusted to follow the length to thickness ratio of 16 ($L/h = 16$) and the extension rate was 2 mm/min. The span of supporting members was adjusted to follow span to thickness ratio of 16 ($L/h = 16$). For each set of samples flexural modulus and flexural strength were calculated. Flexural modulus was calculated as the tangent slope of the initial linear portion of the load–deflection curve.

Figure 9: Flexural strength and modulus of PLA/sisal composites with different fibre volume fraction.

The flexural strength and modulus of PLA increased significantly with addition of sisal fibres, Figure 9. The flexural strength and modulus of neat PLA were 114 MPa and 3.6 GPa respectively. Composites reinforced with 40 vol.% of untreated sisal fibres had flexural strength and modulus of 236 ± 36 MPa and 9.8 ± 0.95 GPa respectively. Composites reinforced with 60 vol% of sisal fibres showed flexural strength of 279 ± 43 MPa and flexural modulus of 19.4 ± 1.36 GPa.

DMTA

Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis was performed on a Triton Tritec 2000 DMA in single cantilever bending mode at the span of 16 mm at a frequency of 1 Hz, heating rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and temperature range of $20 - 100^\circ\text{C}$. The storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E'') and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) were measured as a function of temperature. Tangents were drawn on the elastic and viscoelastic portions of the curves and the glass transition temperature (T_g) was taken to be at the intersection of the two tangents.

Figure 10: Storage modulus of PLA / sisal fibre composites as a function of temperature and fibre volume fraction.

Figure 10 shows the dynamic storage modulus as a function of temperature of composites with untreated fibres. Compared to neat PLA the dynamic mechanical properties of PLA reinforced sisal fibres were enhanced at both fibre volume fractions investigated. The dynamic storage modulus of composites with 0.4 fibre volume fraction was 10.3 GPa at 25°C . The dynamic storage modulus of composites with 0.6 fibre volume fraction was 18.2 GPa at 25°C . Glass transition temperature is related to the maximum end use temperature of the final thermoplastic product. The glass transition temperature (T_g) was found to decrease with increasing amount of fibres

added into the matrix. Thus the T_g dropped from 62°C for pure PLA to 57°C for PLA with a fibre volume fraction of 0.4 to 53°C for PLA with $V_f = 0.6$.

DISCUSSION

There is no doubt that processing thermoplastic matrix composites is more demanding than for thermosetting matrix composites. PLA, with a glass transition temperature of 62°C, has been prepared in the form of foils to facilitate the manufacture of composites with sisal fibre reinforcement. High volume fractions of up to 60% have been achieved for well aligned fibre composites. The conditions for spherulitic growth of PLA at the fibre surface affects the integrity of the fibre to matrix bond measured in microbond shear tests. This research has demonstrated the effectiveness of simple caustic soda treatment of the fibre bundle surface in enhancing adhesion. Accordingly, the flexural properties of the composites are improved by caustic soda treatment of the fibres. The properties are considerably superior to those of wood [10]. Transferring the laboratory scale manufacture of PLA-sisal composites into a viable industrial process is the subject of future work.

CONCLUSIONS

- Bio-sourced and biodegradable composites with fibre volume fraction of 0.6 were manufactured by compression moulding.
- SEM images revealed good fibre to matrix adhesion
- Caustic soda treatment improved the spherulitic growth and transcrystalline layer formation at sisal fibre to polylactic acid interface. The transcrystalline PLA layer grows faster on NaOH-treated fibres than on untreated fibres. Treated fibres gave transcrystallinity at all cooling rates and annealing temperatures.
- Transcrystallinity develops faster at crystallization temperatures below 120°C.
- Caustic soda treatment improved fibre to matrix adhesion in single fibre composites measured in a microbond shear test.
- Mechanical properties of composites were measured in flexure and mean strengths of up to 279MPa and mean Young's moduli of up to 19.4GPa were achieved.
- Using DMTA the glass transition temperature (T_g) was seen to fall as V_f increases.
- Future work will scale up the manufacture of PLA-sisal composites for the manufacture of industrial components.

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